

Environment and its influence

Panicle transpiration studies in north-eastern Sri Lanka

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During a study of dry season water use of flooded rice in northeastern Sri Lanka, the contribution of the panicles to canopy transpiration was examined. The studies were made on cultivar BG200/75 growing in the Polonnaruwa region.

In June 1982, when the transpiration of BG200/75 was measured, the mean air temperature during the daytime was 30.2°C and mean vapor pressure deficit was 15 mb. Average daily solar radiation was 18.3 MJ/m². There was no rainfall except for one short, intense storm.

Stomatal conductance of panicles and foliage was determined using diffusion porometers, and aerodynamic conductance was estimated from the rates of water loss from wetted replicas of leaves and panicles. These conductances, along with current environmental variables, were used in the Monteith version of the Penman formula for crop transpiration. In addition, direct measurements of

panicle transpiration were made by weighing detached panicles before and after a 10-minute period. Although the technique of weighing detached panicles is said to underestimate transpiration, trends with both methods were similar.

Very little fluctuation in panicle conductance and transpiration was observed during sample days, but a marked decline was associated with panicle ageing (Fig. 1). The highest rates of transpiration from the panicles occurred immediately after emergence. Flowering is from top to bottom of a panicle and takes several days. Transpiration decline in any panicle is probably associated with gradual cessation of flowering and the onset of grain filling. On the crop scale, however, panicle contribution to transpiration does not decline so abruptly because of staggered panicle emergence among tillers. Initial panicle transpiration can be 3 mm/day (Fig. 2). Total crop transpiration at this time can be 9 mm/day, with an additional 2 mm evaporated from irrigation water.

Panicle transpiration is considered a mechanism for maintaining low flower temperature and for reducing sterility. Further work is warranted on conductances and panicle transpiration, in par-

1. Decrease in panicle diffusive conductance (g_p) as panicles age, and the relationship of dry/fresh weight percentages and age.

ticular immediately after emergence, under a range of soil water conditions. Information should be obtained on the quantities and distribution of stomata within the flower structure in a range of genotypes. In addition the aerodynamic conductance of water vapor away from panicles at different degrees of exposure above the crop should be evaluated. □

2. Changes in the daily rate of transpiration from panicles as they age.

ERRATUM

P. L. Mohanty and N. P. Sarma. Fertility restorers for cystosterile stocks. IRRN 8:2 (Apr. 1983), 3-4.

In the table on page 3, under the column heading *Maintainers (non-restorers)*, *Kaveri* should read *Cauvery*. □